

Description of scurvy by Bachstrom (1734)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

Bachstrom seems to be the first person to propose that there is something special in fruits and vegetables so that scurvy “*is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food, and greens; which is alone the true primary cause of the disease.*” James Lind firmly disagreed with such a supposition. This is James Lind’s English summary of the text that was originally published in Latin.

Jo. Freder. Bachstrom, a Dutch physician.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/552/mode/2up>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Johann_Bachstrom

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bachstrom_Point

“Bachstrom Point ... named ... in 1959 for Johann Bachstrom, the author in 1734 of a classic pamphlet recognizing scurvy as a nutritional deficiency disease and prescribing the necessary measures for its prevention and cure.”

Siege of Thorn

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siege_of_Thorn_\(1703\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siege_of_Thorn_(1703))

[https://www.wikiwand.com/en/map/Siege_of_Thorn_\(1703\)](https://www.wikiwand.com/en/map/Siege_of_Thorn_(1703))

[https://dbpedia.org/page/Siege_of_Thorn_\(1703\)](https://dbpedia.org/page/Siege_of_Thorn_(1703))

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Great_Northern_War

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_Toru%C5%84

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Toru%C5%84>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections.

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Background

George Yagi Jr. Surviving the wilderness: the diet of the British Army and the struggle for Canada, 1754–1760.

Journal of the Society for Army Historical Research. 2011;89:66-86.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/44231817>

p.72

As early as 1734, Dr. John **Bachstrom**, a physician from Holland, had argued that scurvy was the due to ‘the absence of fresh (or “recent”) vegetable food from the diet for a considerable time.’ Monro's observations in Germany proved that Bachstrom's argument was correct. A simple solution was provided in 1751 by John Wesley, who advised those afflicted with the disease to ‘Live on turnips for a month.’ Ultimately, as hinted by Wesley, the most effective cure and defence against scurvy rested on the procu

Baron JH. Sailors’ scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment.

Nutr Rev. 2009 Jun;67(6):315-32.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2009.00205.x>

p.317

In 1734, Johann **Bachstrom** of Leyden (1686–1742) was one of the first to declare land scurvy and sea scurvy to be identical diseases and to attribute their cause to a deficiency of fresh vegetables, and therefore curable by fresh herbs, fruits, and berries.

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In his chronological abstracts, Lind clearly stated Kramer and **Bachstrom**’s unitary fresh vegetables hypothesis for cause and cure of scurvy. However, his own chapters on the causes and cures of scurvy are full of obscure and uncritical concepts, and one is left with his ideas that sea scurvy was due to excess perspiration, could be prevented by ventilation, and that many remedies could be used as well as citrus fruits and cresses.

Carpenter KJ. The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C. 1986, p.249.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/academic/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

p.44-45

In 1734, a very different evaluation was proposed, again from Holland, by **John Bachstrom**, a physician whose name does not appear in the standard histories of medicine. He postulated that there was only one cause of scurvy – the absence of fresh (or “recent”) vegetable food from the diet for a considerable time. There was no reason to suppose that a cold climate had anything to do with the disease because sailors in the Dutch East Indies fleet developed scurvy in the Tropics. Moreover, in the relatively recent siege of Thorn (Torun, Copernicus’s birthplace in Poland), many thousands of the garrison and inhabitants developed the disease; even though it took place in summer. (It lasted from mid-May to October 4, 1703) The besieging Swedes remained healthy, and those in the town quickly recovered when they had access to fresh greens and vegetables. Nor was there reason to suppose that damp or coastal conditions were required: At the end of a

campaign against the Turks, Austrian troops had spent the winter of 1719 – 20 in a devastated, inland part of Hungary and there had been a heavy loss of life from scurvy. No drugs were of any help, but with the coming of spring there were fresh green foods available and the men recovered. He gave other examples and urged the value of all kinds of green foods and fresh fruit, and recommended a diet rich in green vegetables as a preventive. He said that mineral acids, and specifically the popular sulfuric acid, were useless. With regard to niter he reserved judgment because it was a natural component of plants.

Bachstrom's treatise seems to the modern reader a straightforward argument and one that deserved at least a serious consideration. But to the contemporary main-line physician it would not have been very impressive because it dealt with a single disease in isolation and did nothing toward establishing a view of the nature of disease in general – an ideal which the medical profession had as its goal, by analogy with the universal laws being developed by the physicists at that time. In other words, he was “a mere empirick.”

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[Harriette] Chick has written that “to **Bachstrom** and Lind must go the recognition of scurvy as a nutritional deficiency disease.”¹ However, Lind made it quite clear that he did not accept Bachstrom's “supposition that ... the constitution of the human body, is such that health and life cannot be preserved long, without the use of green herbage, vegetables, and fruits; and that a long abstinence from these, is alone the cause of the disease.” [See below]

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a paper read by Dr. Jean-Antoine Villemin. He is remembered today for his demonstrations nearly a decade earlier that tuberculosis was an infectious disease which could be transmitted from humans to animals and then from one animal to another. At the time, it had been thought to arise spontaneously as a consequence of the weakening effects of a poor environment, inadequate diet, and other debilitating conditions. For a long time, his work was either contested or ignored. We can see the influence of his previous experience in his analysis of scurvy. He made extensive use of the published literature, and argued from it on the following lines (here condensed and paraphrased):

Scurvy is a contagious miasm, comparable to typhus, which occurs in epidemic form when people are closely congregated in large groups as in prisons, naval vessels and sieges. Admittedly, those in strongest condition are most resistant but **it is ridiculous to suppose that a lack of fresh vegetables is the cause of the disease.** It has been alleged that lack of potatoes was the cause of the outbreak in Western Europe in 1847; but some people must go without potatoes every year. As Lind said, **in refuting this kind of argument from **Bachstrom**,** there are many parts such as the Highlands of Scotland where vegetables are unavailable for six months at a time. And how can one explain the health of people in Greenland where they do not grow vegetables at any time? I [Villemin] have also kept a variety of animals in good health without providing them with any of the types of food which are considered antiscorbutic. The 1847 epidemic gradually spread eastwards, reaching Russia in 1848, killing 68,000 people in that year, and hanging on in small pockets after that.

1 Chick H. Early Investigations of Scurvy and the Antiscorbutic Vitamin. Proceedings of the Nutrition Society. 1953;12(3):210-219. <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530050>

Certainly, fresh vegetables and lemon juice have a certain curative value, but do we, just because quinine can cure malaria, conclude that the cause of malaria is a deficiency of quinine? ...

p.251

... the people such as **Bachstrom**, Lind, Elliotson, Budd, and Holst, who made contributions and drew conclusions that we now consider well founded, seem equally consistently to have escaped the usual marks of general recognition and appreciation.

Norris J. The scurvy disposition: heavy exertion as an exacerbating influence on scurvy in modern times. *Bulletin of the History of Medicine* 1983;57:325–38.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/44441613>

p.328-329

Perhaps the last notable example of this view, before the pathology of scurvy was overborne by the ptomaine thesis of Torup, was that of Thomas Colon, Fleet Surgeon to the Nares Arctic expedition of 1875-76, who, after attributing the long-term cause of scurvy on the expedition to the lack of fresh vegetables, fresh meat and lime juice, wrote:

Any one of the following may have acted as a predisposing cause or causes;- Our long dark winter, the confinement between decks in a damp atmosphere for the long period I have mentioned, the extreme changes of temperature undergone during the prevalence of the great cold. The exciting cause I can only attribute to the heavy physical work undergone. The passage over the frozen sea was of the heaviest description.

Perhaps the only notable dissident from this view among those who had viewed the disease first-hand, was J.F. **Bachstrom** (1734), who, on the basis of his observations of scurvy at the siege of Thorn (1703), and elsewhere, concluded: "... the evil is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food and greens, which is alone the primary cause of the disease."

Scott and Scurvy. *Can Med Assoc J.* 1962 Jul 7;87(1):32-3.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1849291>

In 1734 Johannes **Bachstrom** published an 85-page booklet in which he showed that sea scurvy and land scurvy were a single disease whose primary cause was lack of fresh fruits and vegetables. He invented the word antiscorbutic and stated unequivocally that only fresh herbs, fruit and vegetables had this property. He therefore advised sailors to carry more fresh vegetables in their stores and suggested that besieged soldiers should grow antiscorbutic plants from seeds upon their ramparts. Bachstrom's views were not widely accepted. In his day many thought that scurvy was putrescent, an infectious disease. They ascribed it to using the wrong sort of salt for preserving meat.

Chick H. Early Investigations of Scurvy and the Antiscorbutic Vitamin.
Proceedings of the Nutrition Society. 1953;12(3):210-219.
<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530050>

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Bachstrom (1734), in his justly prized pamphlet, after reviewing the available evidence on the causes of scurvy, stated his belief that 'From want of proper attention to the history of the scurvy, its causes have been generally, though wrongfully, supposed to be, cold in northern climates, sea air, the use of salt meats, etc.: whereas this evil is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food, and greens; which is alone the primary cause of the disease', These foods, described as 'antiscorbutic' are declared to be alone its effective cure. It is to **Bachstrom** that we owe the dramatic tale of the helpless 'sailor in the Greenland ships ... so over-run and disabled with the scurvy' that his comrades put him on shore to perish. He having 'quite lost the use of his limbs ... could only crawl about on the ground. This he found covered with a plant, which he, continually grazing like a beast of the field, plucked up with his teeth. In a short time he was by this means fully recovered; and, upon his returning home, it was found to have been the herb scurvy-grass' (translations given by Lind, 1753, pp. 409, 411). Scurvy-grass (*Cochlearia officinalis*), whose habitat is the 'muddy sea shore', is a plant of the Cruciferae, a natural order which contains many of our common green vegetables, including the cabbage and the swede turnip, both of which possess a high antiscorbutic potency. An old religious tradition ascribed the food value of these crucifers to the arrangement of their four petals in the form of a cross.

p.212

To **Bachstrom** and Lind must be given credit for the correct recognition of scurvy as a nutritional deficiency disease and of the measures necessary for its prevention and cure ...

Kark RM. Ascorbic Acid in Relation to Cold, Scurvy, ACTH and Surgery.
Proceedings of the Nutrition Society. 1953;12(3):279-293.
<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530059>

p.280

Lind (1753) also emphasized the importance of cold and its associated stresses as aetiological factors in scurvy, even though he had read **Bachstrom** (1734), who clearly indicated that cold and allied stresses play no part in producing the disease. Bachstrom had studied and reported an epidemic of scurvy which, appearing in the height of the summer of 1703, decimated 5000 of the besieged inhabitants of Thon, in Prussia.

Drummond JC. Historical studies of English diet and nutrition: Lecture III.
Journal of the Royal Society of Arts 1938;86:246-58.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/41361208>

p.247-248

Scurvy in the Eighteenth Century

If the mild form of scurvy, which had come to be known as land-scurvy, became less prevalent than it had been for many centuries previously, the same could

not be said for the dreaded sea-scurvy. It was the scourge of our Navy and our Mercantile Marine. Every account of the voyages of those days has its story of the ravages of scurvy. Every commander or ship's surgeon had his own ideas how best to treat it. Most people still held that it was due to prolonged subsistence on salt food, lack of exercise, the harmful influence of sea air, etc., but although the curative action of fruits, particularly oranges, lemons and limes, was widely recognised, the disease was in no way associated with a deficiency of something which those foods contained. There was one doctor, however, who studied the subject carefully and came to that conclusion. **Bachstrom**, the famous Dutch physician, published an account of the disease and its treatment in 1734. In this little volume it is clearly stated that "Causam Veram et primariam Scorbuti nullam aliam esse, quam abstentiam diuturniorem a quocunque genere recentium vegetabilium." Nothing could be more definite. **It seems to be the first suggestion that the disease was caused by a deficiency in the diet.** It not only made little impression at the time, but it was almost ignored by the medical profession for more than a century. The medical writings of the period on the subject of scurvy are voluminous and confusing. Most of them are mere circumlocution, reiterating the old arguments. Is the disease due to the eating of salt meat? What part does confinement aboard ship play? Are sea-air and mists dangerous? It is easy to appreciate now, how their minds worked in days when the miasma of marshes was regarded as the cause of agues and fevers, and when confinement was believed to be the chief cause of gaol-fever. The literature of the period gives us one other outstanding work on scurvy, namely, the careful and critical study of Dr. James Lind, a naval surgeon, with many years' experience of the disease. It is so remarkable a work that it alone might well form the subject of a group of three Cantor Lectures. Unfortunately, the space at my disposal does not permit me to make more than passing reference to the views expressed in this classic. Lind examined the various theories of the causation of scurvy, one by one, and finds most of them inadequate. How can salt be the chief cause, he asks, when the workers in the salt mines of Poland never get the disease? **Bachstrom** claims that the disease results from the absence of fresh vegetables from the diet. Surely this cannot be wholly true, otherwise those who live in the North of Europe and in Newfoundland would suffer, since they are often without fresh fruits and vegetables for four or five months in the year. He did not suspect what we know to-day, namely, that these people are in a state bordering on scurvy when the long winter ends.

Martin GJ, Heise FH. Vitamin C nutrition in pulmonary tuberculosis. American Journal of Digestive Diseases and Nutrition. 1937;4:368-374. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02999935>

p.372

... **Bachstrom** in 1734 (Observationes circa scorbutum) noted a relationship of tuberculosis and vitamin C nutrition. He stated that scurvy could be cured by fresh vegetables provided tuberculosis was not a complicating factor. The relationship has been assumed but not definitely established.

Stockman R. James Lind and Scurvy. Edinb Med J. 1926;33(6):329-350.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5302666>

p.344

On the Continent, ... **Bachstrom** published (1734) a small book of considerable value in which he asserts that abstinence from fresh vegetables is the one and only cause.

Hess AF. Scurvy, Past and Present, 1920.
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

p.3

In an essay published in the eighteenth century (1734), **Bachstrom** described an epidemic of scurvy which occurred in 1703 during the siege of Thorn, in Prussia, by the Swedes, which caused the death of 5000 of the garrison, in addition to a large number of the inhabitants. It is interesting to note that this epidemic took place in the middle of the summer, and not in the cold season.

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7mfk27h/items?canvas=15>

p.144

Bachstrom (Observationes circa Scorbutum, 1734) evidently was well-acquainted with the antiscorbutic value of scurvy grass, and relates the story of a sailor severely disabled from scurvy who was put ashore to perish on Greenland, and crawled on the ground, grazed on scurvy grass like a beast of the field, and was able to return home perfectly recovered. (Cited from Lind.)

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7mfk27h/items?canvas=162>

James Lind's comments on Bachstrom:

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...

But the contrary is demonstratively evinced, by the deplorable case of the sailor left behind at *Greenland*, related by **Bachstrom** and others, who was cured by scurvy-grass alone;

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/28/mode/2up>

p.33

[whether the land scurvy and sea scurvy are different]

... The cure of scorbutic diseases contracted either at land or sea, is entirely the same. This will appear to any person who peruses **Bachstrom's** and *Kramer's* observations, and several other histories related in this treatise.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/32/mode/2up>

p.44-45

Thus, where the causes productive of it [scurvy] are general, and violent in a high degree, it becomes an *epidemic* or universal calamity, and rages with great and diffusive virulence: as happens often to seamen in long voyages; sometimes to armies (Nitzsch), very lately to the *German* soldiers in *Hungary* (*Kramer*); frequently to troops when closely besieged, as to the *Saxon* garrison in *Thorn* (**Bachstrom**), the besieged in *Breda* (*Vander Mye*), in *Rochelle*, as also *Stetin*: and at other times to whole countries; as in *Brabant*, in the year 1556; and in *Holland*, ann. 1562.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/44/mode/2up>

p.50

Others, again have supposed such to be the constitution of the human body, that health and life cannot be preserved long, without the use of green herbage, vegetables and fruits; and that a long abstinence from these, is alone the cause of the disease (**Bachstrom**).

But if this were truly the case, we must have had the scurvy very accurately described

by the antients; whose chief study seems to have been the art of war; and whose manner of besieging towns was generally by blockade, till they had forced a surrender by famine. Now, as they held out many months, sometimes years, without a supply of vegetables: we should, no doubt, have heard of many dying of the scurvy, long before the magazines of dry provisions were exhausted. The continuance of those sieges far exceeded most of our modern ones; even the five months blockade of *Thorn*, upon which *Bachstrom* had founded this supposition. It would likewise be a much more frequent disease in every country, than it really is: for there are persons every where, who, from choice, eat few or no green vegetables; and some countries are deprived of the use of them for five or six months of the year; as is the case of many parts in the highlands of *Scotland*, *Newfoundland*, &c. where, however, the scurvy is unusual.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/50/mode/2up>

p.81-82

Moreover, the same causes when subsisting at land, have been found sometimes to give rise to as violent scurvies as those at sea (Vander Mye). Thus during the siege of *Thorn* in the year 1703, several thousand *Saxons* shut up in that city were cutoff by it at the latter end of the siege, they having been blockaded for five months, the season appears to have been uncommonly tempestuous and rainy, over most parts of Europe: so that, in this situation, the inconveniences and hardships they suffered, must have been equal to those of seamen. They were continually exposed to unwholesome damp weather; their diet was gross and indigestible, as *ammunition*-bread, salted and dried meats, and other solid and coarse food; which they were at that time obliged to live upon, being deprived of vegetables.

We are told (**Bachstrom**), that when some few of the coarsest and most common greens were permitted to be brought into the town, by agreement entered into with the enemy, they were voraciouly devoured by the officers at the gates, as the greatest delicacies. The inhabitants, indeed, ascribed the calamity [scurvy] to the unwholesome beer in the city. But it was observable, it attacked and cut off first the *Saxon* garrison, who were most exposed to the inclemency of the weather, by doing hard duty night and day upon the walls. The inhabitants, who remained in warmer lodgings, were much later taken ill of it; and probably only those, who, upon the garrison's being almost destroyed, were obliged to do military duty.

This was a real scurvy; and no sooner the gates were opened, and plenty of vegetables admitted upon the surrender of the town, but the disease quickly disappeared, after having occasioned a very dreadful mortality.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/80/mode/2up>

p.140

This precept becomes still more necessary, when the garrison's provisions in store are spoiled or unsound; in which case the use of vinegar is recommended by several authors. **Bachstrom's** advice, of sowing the seeds of the antiscorbutic plants, so that they may grow up with the grass on the ramparts², will, upon this occasion, be found very beneficial. They can indeed be under no difficulty in procuring some of the most salutary of them at all times, if they are provided with their seeds, such as the garden-cresses; which in a few days, even in their apartments, will supply them with a fresh antiscorbutic salad.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/140/mode/2up>

2 Rampart. A length of embankment or wall forming part of the defensive boundary of a castle, hillfort, settlement or other fortified site. It is usually broad-topped and made of excavated earth and/or masonry.
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rampart_\(fortification\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rampart_(fortification))

p.159-160

We are told, that at the siege of *Thorn*, when this calamity raged with great violence in the town, it was the last and most earnest petition of the diseased, that some of these fruits might be permitted to enter their gates, as the only hopes of life, and last comfort of the dying patient (**Bachstrom**).

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/160/mode/2up>

The text on the following pages is the summary by Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.399-405.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/398/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/398/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=423>

<https://hdl.handle.net/2027/ucm.5320216006>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=421>

The original in **Latin**:

Observationes circa scorbutum; ejusque indolem, causas, signa, et curam.

Auctore Joanne Fred. Bachstrom.

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb10470543?page=,1>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/sz87299c>

<https://archive.org/details/b30517448>

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_bj8_AAAAcAAJ

Translation to **English**:

<https://www.evidentia.net/book/bachstrom-observations-on-scurvy>

“This work by Johann **Bachstrom** (1686-1742) is the first European publication to have established scurvy primarily as a deficiency disease (due to the lack of fresh vegetables and fruit). But this work, never before translated from Latin into English, has remained virtually unknown in the English-speaking world. Bachstrom, an Enlightenment figure, scientist and Lutheran pastor from Poland who fearlessly defied social conventions and the “powers that be” throughout his life, was ultimately strangled to death on the orders of the Jesuits.”

1734

*Observationes circa scorbutum;
ejusque indolem, causas, signa, et curam.
Auctore Joanne Fred. Bachstrom.*

p.399

From want of proper attention to the history of the scurvy, its causes have been generally, though wrongfully, supposed to be, cold in northern climates, sea-air, the use of salt meats, &c. whereas this evil is solely owing to a total abstinence from fresh vegetable food, and greens; which is alone the true primary cause of the disease. And where persons, either through neglect or from necessity, refrain for a considerable time from eating the fresh fruits of the earth, and greens, no age, no climate or soil, are exempted from its attack. Other secondary causes may likewise concur: but recent vegetables are found alone effectual to preserve the body from this malady; and most speedily to cure it, even in a few days, when the case is not rendered desperate by the patient's being dropsical³ or consumptive. All which is founded on the following observations.

p.400

He remarks, that the scurvy is most frequent among northern nations, and in the coldest countries. There it is not confined to the sea alone, but rages with great violence at land, afflicting both natives and foreigners; of which the poor seamen left to winter in *Greenland*, who were all cut off by this distemper, afford a memorable instance. But the opinion of its being produced there by cold, he thinks irre-

3 Dropsy.

The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek *hydrops* (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included *hydrothorax* (fluid in the chest cavity), *ascites* (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), *anasarca* (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

Scurvy can cause heart failure, eg.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10949735>

conciliable with the daily experience of its attacking seamen in their voyages to the *Indies*, even when under the torrid zone.

That it is not peculiar to the sea, the following histories sufficiently evince. During the late siege of *Thorn*, above 5 or 6000 of the garrison, besides a great number of the inhabitants, died of this distemper; the surrender of the town being more owing to the havock made by this dreadful calamity, than to the bravery of the besiegers. Upon which he observes, that, allowing this disease to be most frequent among the northern nations in winter, yet, the siege of that place was carried on in the heat of summer; and the *Swedes*, the besiegers, a northern nation, kept altogether free from the scurvy. The mischief first attacked chiefly the blockaded *Saxon* garrison. They being almost all cut off, the inhabitants were at last obliged to do duty upon the walls; of whom it also destroyed

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a great number. But no sooner was the siege raised, and the gates of the town open for the admission of vegetables and greens from the country, but the mortality quickly ceased, and the disease at once disappeared.

In the end of the last war with the *Turks*, when the Imperial army wintered in *Hungary*, the country having been laid waste about *Temeswere*⁴, by the calamities of the preceding war, many thousands of the common soldiers (but not one officer, as having a different diet) were cut off by the scurvy. The physician to that army⁵ employed his utmost skill, and used the most approved antiscorbutic remedies. Notwithstanding which, the mortality went on increasing during the winter. Unacquainted with the disease, or rather its remedy, he demanded a consultation of the college of physicians at *Vienna* for the preservation of the troops; whose prescriptions and advice were of no service. The disease still persisted with increasing virulence until the spring, that the earth was covered with greens and vegetables. And the physician now rejoiced as much in having found out the true cause of this evil, as before he had regretted his unhappy disappointment in the removal of so general and dreadful a calamity.

As some are of opinion, that warm and inland countries are altogether free from
p.402

this distemper, he gives an account from an officer of a *German* garrison in *Italy*, where many of the soldiers were cut off by it at a great distance from the sea. The officer himself, an *Italian*, was miserably afflicted, and given over by his physicians, who were altogether ignorant of his case; when a *German* surgeon, by lucky accident passing that way, rescued him from the jaws of death. He cured him in a few days, to the surprise of his physicians, by ordering his servant to the fields to supply

him with green vegetables, especially the *sisymbrium*⁶ or red water mint, which grew thereabouts very plentifully.

The following relation is no less curious. A sailor in the *Greenland* ships was so overrun and disabled with the scurvy, that his companions put him into a boat, and sent him on shore; leaving him there to perish, without the least expectation of a recovery. The poor wretch had quite lost the use of his limbs; he could only crawl about on the ground. This he found covered with a plant, which he, continually grazing like a beast of the field, plucked up with his teeth. In a short time he was by this means perfectly recovered; and, upon his returning home, it was found to be the herb scurvy-grass.

From all which the author concludes, that as abstinence from recent vegetables is
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altogether and solely the cause of the distemper, so these alone are its effectual remedies.⁷ Accordingly he bestows the epithet of *antiscorbutic* on all of that class which are wholesome and eatable; observing Nature every where affords a supply of remedies, even in *Greenland*, and the most frozen countries. There no sooner the snow melts from the rivers, but their borders are covered with brooklime, cresses, and scurvy-grass, in ample prodigality. There Nature dictates to those barbarous nations, that what she thus blesses them with in such bounteous profusion, affords present health and relief in their malady. Of this all physicians acquainted with the nature of the scurvy, must be likewise sensible. The most common herbs and fresh fruits excel the most pompous medicines, especially

4 Apparently indicates "Temesvar"
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_Timi%C8%99oara

5 Kramer <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17224830>

6 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sisymbrium>

7 Lind firmly disagrees with the supposition that fruit and vegetables are solely the cause of scurvy, see above p.50.

those of the animal and mineral kinds. He divides antiscorbutics into three classes. The first contains the common pot-herbs, and all plants of an insipid, or rather sweetish taste, fruits of trees, &c. of this quality; and when in want of those, even grass itself may be eat. In the second class, he ranks all vegetables, roots, fruits, berries, &c. that are of a tart or acid taste: and these being of a middling, quality betwixt the insipid plants of the first class, and the stronger bitters he includes in the third, they will prove more effectual than the first,

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without being liable to some inconveniencies which may attend those of the third class. In this last he comprehends all fresh herbs, roots, and fruits, of a bitter and strong taste, of the nature of scurvygrass, cresses, &c. These last are with caution to be prescribed at first, or in great quantities. **For prevention he recommends living much upon green vegetables**, when they can be got; otherwise, upon preserved fruits, herbs, roots, &c. **He advises seamen when at land**

to be more careful of laying up a store of greens than of flesh; and, in case of necessity, would have them when at sea to make trial of the sea-weeds that grow upon the ship's bottom; being persuaded, that the great physician of nature had not left them without a remedy, although he had never heard of its being tried⁸. After a long abstinence from vegetables, the diseased are to begin with the milder antiscorbutics, proceeding by degrees to those of a stronger nature. In examining the mineral and fossil remedies, which have been so much recommended for the scurvy, he observes of nitre, that as it is a copious ingredient in most plants, it may perhaps be serviceable; but otherwise, all those classes are to be avoided. He condemns the use of steel, mercury, and alum; as likewise

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sulphureous and vitriolic⁹ medicines, especially the strong acid of vitriol, which some account a specific in the scurvy; but they will find themselves disappointed.

8 I am informed they were tried in Lord Anson's ship.

9 Oil of Vitriol. Sulfuric acid.

"Sulfuric acid, known in antiquity as oil of vitriol"

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitriol>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sulfuric_acid

Elixir of vitriol: A mixture of sulfuric acid and alcohol, once prescribed as a treatment for scurvy.

https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/elixir_of_vitriol